

THIRD DECLENSION IS A CATEGORY OF NOUNS IN LATIN AND GREEK

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Introduction. With broadly similar case formation — diverse stems, but similar endings. Sanskrit also has a corresponding class (although not commonly termed as third), in which the so-called basic case endings are applied very regularly.

In contrast with the first- and second-declension endings, those of the third declension lack a theme vowel (a or o/u in the first and second declensions) and so are called athematic.

One distinguishing feature of third-declension nouns is a genitive singular ending of a short vowel and s: Latin *rēg-is* "of a king" Greek *χειρ-ός* (*cheir-ós*) "of a hand", and Sanskrit *bhagavat-as* "of the blessed (one)". Another is a dative singular ending of *i* (short *i* in Greek, long *ī* in Latin): *rēg-ī* "for a king"; *χειρ-ί* (*cheir-í*) "for, with the hand". This corresponds to an *-e* ending in Sanskrit, which might have been a contracted *ai* or lengthened *i*: *bhagavat-e* "for the blessed (one)"

Grammatical gender manifests itself when words related to a noun like determiners, pronouns or adjectives change their form (inflect) according to the gender of noun they refer to (agreement).

The masculine gender refers to any noun or pronoun that is used to refer to people and animals classified as male.

Case ending (plural case endings) (grammar, in nouns and adjectives that inflect to mark grammatical case) A suffix-like element which indicates a word's grammatical case, number, and gender.

Coordinate adjectives are two or more adjectives of equal value that are used to describe the same noun. They are separated by the word 'and' or a comma. Writers know they are working with the coordinate adjective when the adjectives may be written in reverse order with 'and' between them.

You have more than 600 muscles in your body. Some muscles help you move, lift or sit still. Others help you digest food, breathe or see. Your heart is a muscle that

pumps blood through your body. Many injuries and diseases can affect how the muscles work. To keep your muscles strong, maintain a healthy weight, eat right and exercise regularly.

Third declension is a category of nouns in Latin and Greek with broadly similar case formation — diverse stems, but similar endings. Sanskrit also has a corresponding class (although not commonly termed as third), in which the so-called basic case endings are applied very regularly.

In contrast with the first- and second-declension endings, those of the third declension lack a theme vowel (a or o/u in the first and second declensions) and so are called athematic.

One distinguishing feature of third-declension nouns is a genitive singular ending of a short vowel and s: Latin *rēg-is* "of a king" Greek *χειρ-ός* (*cheir-ós*) "of a hand", and Sanskrit *bhagavat-as* "of the blessed (one)". Another is a dative singular ending of *i* (short *i* in Greek, long *ī* in Latin): *rēg-ī* "for a king"; *χειρ-ί* (*cheir-í*) "for, with the hand". This corresponds to an *-e* ending in Sanskrit, which might have been a contracted *ai* or lengthened *i*: *bhagavat-e* "for the blessed (one)"

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